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Is Technetium-99- 2-methoxyisobutylisonitrile uptake in newly diagnosed multiple myeloma correlated with extense of disease activity?

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Technetium-99m 2-methoxyisobutylisonitrile (Tc-99m-MIBI) has been proposed as a useful tracer for the detection of disease sites in patients with multiple myeloma (MM).

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the role of the Tc-99m-MIBI uptake in disease detection and to assess the correlation between the uptake of this scintigraphy agent and prognostic factors in newly diagnosed MM patients.

Thirty-two untreated patients with multiple myeloma were studied using Tc-99m-MIBI. Anterior and posterior whole-body imaging were obtained 10 min after I.V. injection of 370 MBq Tc-99m-MIBI and scored according to intensity (I) and extent (E) of the radiotracer uptake. A summed score (SS) for the Tc-99m MIBI scan was calculated for each patient. The correlation between known prognostic factors of MM and a SS of Tc-99m-MIBI uptake was assessed.

There was a positive correlation between a SS of Tc-99m-MIBI uptake and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR; $r=0.553$, $P = 0.001$), C-reactive protein (CRP; $r=0.434$, $P = 0.01$), β_2 -microglobulin (β_2M ; $r=0.358$, $P = 0.04$), fibrinogen ($r=0.463$, $P = 0.008$) and bone marrow plasma cell infiltration ($r=0.613$, $P = 0.0001$). An inverse correlation was found between a SS of Tc-99m-MIBI uptake and hemoglobin ($r=0.442$, $P = 0.012$) and serum albumin ($r=0.603$, $P = 0.0003$).

In conclusion, the results of this study suggest that a higher uptake of the radiotracer correlated with more extensive disease activity, as determined by high levels of CRP, β_2M , fibrinogen and bone marrow plasma cell infiltration.

Key words: Multiple Myeloma; Diagnostic Imaging; Technetium Tc 99m Sestamibi; Prognosis

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Comparison of left ventricular functional parameters evaluated by quantitative ECG-gated SPECT and echocardiography

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Introduction: Prognosis and therapeutic decisions are often based on functional parameters of left ventricle (LV) such as: end-diastolic volume (EDV), end-systolic volume (ESV) and LV ejection fraction (LVEF), which means that these parameters need to be accurately measured. This can be done by many imaging modalities. Each of these modalities is subject to measurement errors that can lead to the inaccurate calculation of these parameters. The aim of this study was to compare the LV functional parameters calculated using quantitative electrocardiography (ECG)-gated myocardial perfusion single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) with those measured by ultrasound echocardiography (UCG).

Methods: We examined 40 patients (20 men and 20 women). In both groups we had the same number of patients with and without the presence of prior myocardial infarction. By the gated SPECT using technetium (Tc)-99m methoxyisobutylisonitrile (MIBI) perfusion and 4DM software, we calculated the following parameters: LV end-diastolic volume (EDV), end-systolic volume (ESV), ejection fraction (EF). The same parameters were measured by UCG. The measurements were performed within 6 month of each other. No new cardiac events were registered and no interventions were performed between measuring. The correlations between the cardiac parameters by UCG and those by SPECT/4DM were examined by linear regression analysis. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results: There was a significant correlation between EDV, ESV and EF measured by SPECT/MIBI and UCG (EDV, $r = 0.71$, $p < 0.001$; ESV, $r = 0.82$, $p < 0.001$; EF, $r = 0.75$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The LV systolic and diastolic parameters evaluated by SPECT/4DM correlated with those by UCG. The SPECT/4DM offers useful information regarding functional parameters of left ventricle in both men and women. Although the correlation between values obtained with gated-SPECT and blood pool ventriculography was acceptable, the differences show that the two techniques cannot be considered equivalent.

Key words: Cardiac-Gated Single-Photon Emission Computed-Assisted Tomography; Echocardiography; Myocardial Perfusion Imaging; Gated Blood-Pool Imaging; Ventricular Function, Left